

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

STUDY OF THE ELASTIC IMPACT OF A SPHERICAL OBJECT ON A VERTICAL PLATE

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ABSTRACT

This article is about studying the vibrations of objects hitting a vertical plate in order to assess the possible damage required for the restoration of areas affected by the destruction and explosions during the earthquake. The energy reflection coefficient, which describes the wave reflected from a metal object, is studied. Investigation opens up opportunities for the development of devices with unique properties.

Keywords: study, elastic impact, spherical object.

We will use the principle of similarity, when a model with small-scale objects can be transferred to real objects in size. Even casual scaling will be appropriate when used in practice for the work of the mechanisms shown in the **Figure**. The experimental setup

is shown in the **Figure** where an object is shown swinging on a *string tied to a tripod and hits the metal body at the base*.

Figure. A metal object fixed on a horizontal stand receives impacts from a spherical ball deflected at angles of deviation from the equilibrium position, which is measured using a protractor attached to the tripod.

Fundamentals and Principles of the Investigation

The impact of two objects with masses m_1 and m_2 , velocities v_1 and v_2 will result in the creation of a total momentum of two bodies with masses m_1 and m_2 along the straight line which involves the impact action from the array of objects with velocities u_1 and u_2 . The law of conservation of momentum for the masses moving on the straight line can be written in the form

$$\frac{m_1 v_1^2}{2} + \frac{m_2 v_2^2}{2} = \frac{m_1 u_1^2}{2} + \frac{m_2 u_2^2}{2}$$

$$\Delta S = \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 \Delta \varepsilon_i^2 / (5(5-1)) \right)^{1/2}$$

Also the law of conservation of kinetic energy will have the form

$$\frac{m_1 v_1^2}{2} + \frac{m_2 v_2^2}{2} = \frac{m_1 u_1^2}{2} + \frac{m_2 u_2^2}{2}$$

The last two laws can be rewritten in the form

$$m_1(v_1 - u_1) = m_2(u_2 - v_2)$$

$$m_1(v_1^2 - u_1^2) = m_2(u_2^2 - v_2^2)$$

Since that the velocity of the second body before the elastic impact may be considered zero, we obtain the form for the velocity of the first body [1]:

$$u_1 = \frac{(m_1 - m_2)v_1}{m_1 + m_2}$$

The latter relationship makes it possible to estimate the velocity of a body with mass before and after impact. The coefficient of restitution is used, which is a measure of the elasticity of the impact in the following form:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{u_1}{v_1}$$

The latter expression uses the components of the velocity of a spherical object perpendicular to the direction of motion, which are defined as the sides of a right triangle, which forms the hypotenuse in the form of the direction of the weight vector and the side of the perpendicular direction. Moreover, the angle of deflection of a spherical object in a right triangle is equal to half the angle of deflection of a spherical object that oscillates suspended on a string.

The oscillations occur symmetrically about the centre line which is vertical in the direction of gravity and symmetrical about the direction of the vertical force. The deviation of the string about the vertical can be divided into two equal parts, one of which corresponds to the movement from the direction to the straight line in the direction of gravity.

If the impact is elastic, then the energy corresponding to the wave velocity m_2 incident on the solid

is proportional to the angle of deviation from the vertical of the direction of gravity. In this case, the recovery will depend only on the angle of deviation from the vertical and the formula according [1] for it will be

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sin(\varphi_{u1}/2)}{\sin(\varphi_{v1}/2)}$$

Model experiment and calculations

Calculation of the arithmetic mean value ε_{mv} of the recovery coefficient using the formula presented in [1], deviation of the arithmetic mean $\Delta\varepsilon_i$ using the formula from [1], absolute error of determining the loss coefficient, as difference between mean value ε_{mv} and calculation for i-th experiment ε_i : $\Delta\varepsilon_i = \varepsilon_{mv} - \varepsilon_i$; calculation of the root mean square deviation of the arithmetic mean value

$$\Delta S = \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 \Delta\varepsilon_i^2 / (5 * (5-1)) \right)^{1/2},$$
 calculation the

relative measurement error in the experiment $\Delta E = \Delta\varepsilon_{mv} / \varepsilon_{mv} * 100\%$ for metallic sphere object and the plastic object are presented in Tables 1 and consequently Table 2 [1]:

Table 1

N	φ_{v1}^0	φ_{u1}^0	ε	$\Delta\varepsilon$	ΔS	$\Delta E, \%$
1	45°	15°	0.341	0.008	0.0213	11.4
2	45°	13°	0.296	0.037		
3	45°	12°	0.273	0.060		
4	45°	17°	0.389	0.056		
5	45°	16°	0.364	0.031		
Mean value			0.333	0.038		

Table 2

N	φ_{v1}^0	φ_{u1}^0	ε	$\Delta\varepsilon$	ΔS	$\Delta E, \%$
1	45°	250	0.564	0.0108	0.0235	5.59
2	45°	300	0.676	0.0412		
3	45°	260	0.587	0.0478		
4	45°	280	0.629	0.0058		
5	45°	320	0.718	0.0832		
Mean value			0.6348	0.0378		

Conclusions

Large-scale modelling allows explore objects in full size and the behaviour of engineering structures promising field that combines science and technology to solve persistent problems of our time. It is important for improving mechanical devices, energy systems, technologies, and civil safety objects, etc. [2 - 4]. Further research in this area opens up prospects for the development of devices and materials also to eliminate the destruction and rebuild of engineering structures.

References

1. Ярицька Л.І., Балицька В.О. Фізичний практикум. Частина І. Механіка. Молекулярна фізика. Львів ЛДУ БЖД. 2018. 143 с.

2. Nikolaevich, K.V., Starodub, Y., Havrys, A. Computer Modeling in the Application to Geothermal Engineering. – Advances in Civil Engineering, 2021.

3. Starodub G., Gnyp A. Models of the earth's crust structure in the east Carpatian region determined from inversion of farfield p-waveforms. Acta Geophysica Polonica, 1999, 47(4), pp. 375–400.

4. Starodub Y., Mykhalichko B., Lavrenyuk H., Kozionova O., Polcik H., Kuplovskiy B. Environmental geo-informational monitoring system for the civil and fire safety services of Ukraine. Visnyk of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Geology, 2024, 2(105), pp. 104–110.